

GROWTH DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH JUVENILE ARTHRITIS

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Abstract. Juvenile arthritis (JA) is a severe destructive and inflammatory disease of the joints, leading to disability of patients. Juvenile arthritis (JA) is characterized by local and generalized growth retardation, as well as the development of periarticular osteoporosis and later generalized bone demineralization, which contributes to an increased incidence of bone fractures. Growth impairment is one of the important medical and social problems, the solution of which in recent years has been given much attention by scientists from different countries of the world and different specialties.

Growth retardation is not only observed in 'classic' SUR, which almost always leads to stunting, in contrast to SA in general. Stunting is also very common in various variants of SRA.

Keywords: SA, juvenile ankylosing spondylitis, stunting, glucocorticosteroids, somatotropes.

Growth impairment is one of the most important medical and social problems, which in recent years has received a lot of attention from scientists from different countries and different specialties. In addition to primary endocrine pathology, severe chronic somatic diseases, including rheumatic diseases and especially juvenile arthritis, can also cause growth retardation. [1].

Juvenile arthritis (JA) is a severe destructive-inflammatory disease of the joints, leading to disability of patients, developing in children under 16 years of age, if other rheumatic diseases are excluded [3].

Juvenile arthritis (JA) is characterized by local and generalized growth retardation, as well as the development of periarticular osteoporosis and later generalized bone demineralization, which contributes to an increased incidence of bone fractures (40). On the one hand, SA, especially its systemic and polyarticular variants, is a serious disease, which is often very severe, fraught with the development of life-threatening conditions and significant functional failure.

Causes of growth impairment in SA and ways of its correction.

The mechanism of stunting development in SA is complex. Early onset of the disease in critical periods of childhood can lead to inhibition and permanent growth retardation in the future; the debut of the disease in later periods entails a slowdown in growth rates, whereas growth is one of the most important parameters of physical health, functional status and quality of life in children. Low growth has a significant impact on the psychological status of the child and often leads to maladaptation, especially in adolescents (Prader, 1886). In recent years, a great interest of scientists, both rheumatologists and endocrinologists, has been directed to the study of disorders of the growth-regulating system in children with various P3s.

According to numerous literature reports, growth impairment is one of the most common problems in children with SA, especially in those who have to receive glucocorticoid (GC) therapy for many years [42,49,50]. The causes of growth impairment in SA are manifold. There is no doubt that constitutional genetic factors influence the growth and physical development of a child, which

are not always taken into account when analyzing the causes of stunting in children with chronic somatic pathology, including SA.

Pathogenetic mechanisms of RA influence the growth-stimulating system. It is assumed that neuroendocrine and immunological mechanisms are closely interrelated in the pathogenesis of RA. Studies conducted in adult patients with RA and adult Still's syndrome have shown that they have a significant increase in serum prolactin levels, while cortisol levels are reduced and continue to decrease with the activity of the immunoinflammatory process. Thus, prolactin has a distinct proinflammatory potential. The role of neuroendocrine interactions in children with chronic RH has been studied to a much lesser extent than in adults. The data currently available suggest that neuroendocrine mechanisms are involved in the pathological process of some RHs, such as juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA), juvenile chronic arthritis (JCA), juvenile ankylosing spondylitis (JAS) [22,27,48]. In children, the largest number of studies has been related to the study of prolactin. Normal prolactin levels have been observed in children with JRA, most of whom were in the inactive stage; higher levels have been noted in children during exacerbations and those with ocular involvement. A trend towards higher prolactin levels was found in children with systemic SUR. High prolactin levels were found in all patients with active JRA. Limited data are available on cortisol levels in children. It has been suggested to be deficient in JRA, similar to studies in adult RA patients. Children with JRA are thought to have a pro-inflammatory hormonal status.

Growth retardation is not only seen in 'classic' JRA, almost always resulting in stunting, in contrast to SA in general. Stunting is also very common in various variants of JRA. Studies by several authors have shown that when JuA manifests in adolescence, the growth of the child stops, despite the increased release of STH during this period [44,51]. This indicates that the activity of the disease itself negatively affects the growth process. We can agree with the opinion of scientists convinced that the leading role in growth retardation of patients with JuA is played by the disease itself, and not by antirheumatic therapy, in particular GC, since as early as 1932. The problem of growth was discussed when GH was unknown and treatment with GH was not yet available. Growth retardation in SA is caused by the disruption of the neuroendocrine axis, even in the absence of GH deficiency, because there is a decrease in the serum concentration of its mediator, IRF I. Among the reasons for this phenomenon, insensitivity of receptors to IRF 1 and the influence of proinflammatory cytokines are discussed, which requires further study [25]. Immunopathological mechanisms underlying inflammation in SA are in close interaction with the growth-regulatory system in the child's body. There is evidence of a direct effect of interleukin 6 (IL-6), one of the leading proinflammatory cytokines in SA, on the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system.

Patients with juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA) in long-term remission were found to have a better nutritional status than healthy individuals [36,37]. A number of researchers, assessing caloric intake and anthropometric data of children with oligoarticular and polyarticular forms of JIA, have shown that there are no differences in protein, fat and carbohydrate intake in these groups. Short stature was observed in both groups, while wasting or obesity was observed in children with polyarticular JRA. Thus, in patients with SUR, especially those with polyarthritis, significant growth impairment and altered nutritional status are likely to be exacerbated by inadequate caloric intake, while caloric and various nutrient requirements increase over the course of the disease [25]. Italian researchers studied growth velocity of 58 patients with JRA with a

disease duration of 4.9-2.8 years who had never received HA. The authors noted that in children with systemic and polyarticular forms of JRA, the duration of the disease and the number of exacerbations had a significant negative effect on growth. It was also shown that patients with grade I functional impairment had less growth retardation than patients with grade I functional impairment. Growth retardation in systemic and polyarticular forms of JRA noted in puberty was significantly greater than in prepubertal period ($p = 0.02$). All this confirms the data of other researchers indicating that a long duration of the disease, a high degree of functional failure and the age of puberty are risk factors for growth retardation in systemic and polyarticular JRA [21].

Effect of glucocorticosteroids on the growth process

The growth process is also influenced by glucocorticosteroids, which are known to have pronounced anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties. Therefore, they are used in the treatment of a wide range of diseases (rheumatic, allergic, oncological, etc.), as well as for the prevention of rejection reactions in transplantology, for the treatment of septic shock, etc. [2,4,5,6,8].

Glucocorticosteroids, being a powerful anti-rheumatic drug, simultaneously have many pronounced side effects (growth retardation, generalized osteoporosis, adrenal cortex atrophy) [7]. The frequency and severity of complications, all other things being equal, are proportional to the duration of treatment and the dose of the drug [5]. Therefore, glucocorticosteroids are used mainly in children with systemic variant of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis when non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and baseline therapy are ineffective. The doses used in this case range from 0.5-1.0 mg per 1 kg of body weight [7]. Treatment with glucocorticosteroids, as a rule, not only impairs growth, but also aggravates the growth inhibition processes caused by the disease. The minimum dose of prednisolone, which does not significantly affect the growth of a child, is considered to be 5 mg/day for 6 months [6]. In addition, glucocorticosteroids have a pronounced and diverse effect on metabolism. In particular, blood sugar content increases, which is associated with more intensive glyconeogenesis in the liver. Utilisation of amino acids for glyconeogenesis leads to inhibition of protein synthesis with preserved or somewhat accelerated catabolism (negative nitrogen balance occurs). Cell proliferation and fibroblast function are also suppressed, which is one of the reasons for the delay of regenerative processes; tissue formation (including bone formation) is impaired and growth is slowed down [10].

Glucocorticosteroids are antagonists of growth hormone in terms of their effect on metabolic processes in the body. With prolonged exposure above physiological doses of glucocorticosteroids, the secretion of both growth hormone and insulin-like factor binding protein and their interaction with the receptor apparatus are significantly impaired [19,28,31,45]. Under conditions of hypercorticism, the release of somatotrophic hormone by the pituitary gland is impaired due to activation of somatostatin influence of the hypothalamus caused by increased B-adrenergic sensitivity of hypothalamic somatostatin neurons. The spontaneous and stimulated levels of somatotrophic hormone secretion in children are largely dependent on the dose and duration of steroid treatment. However, even a prednisolone dose of 0.1 mg/kg/day can lead to impaired growth in children [15]. Glucocorticosteroids have a dual effect on the somatotrophic function of the pituitary gland: a short-term rapid potentiating effect and a delayed prolonged inhibitory effect. The stimulating effect of steroids is mediated through a decrease in somatostatin release, an increase in the sensitivity of pituitary somatotropes to the action of growth hormone releasing factor and activation of somatotrophic hormone gene transcription [21, 26]. On the other

hand, in children who have been receiving glucocorticosteroid therapy for a long time for various diseases, a significant decrease in these parameters compared to the norm was observed during the study of spontaneous secretion, the profile of nocturnal secretion of growth hormone and against the background of pharmacological stimulation tests (with L-dopa and clonidine) [24]. However, according to a number of authors, somatotropic hormone secretion under the influence of glucocorticosteroids changes insignificantly, and growth disturbance is mainly associated with changes in somatomedin regulation or direct inhibitory effect of such therapy on bone [12, 35].

Most often growth retardation develops in children who were administered glucocorticosteroids just before puberty, since it is during this period that the growth rate is the lowest and the secretion of endogenous somatotropic hormone transiently decreases. In addition, suppression of adrenal androgen secretion by exogenous glucocorticosteroids during this period may impair the activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal system, which is necessary for increased secretion of somatotropic hormone and direct stimulation of growth by sex hormones [25]. Consequently, stunting is a characteristic manifestation of hypercorticism of both endogenous and exogenous genesis. Studying the effects of somatotropic hormone is important because growth retardation is often observed in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. The reasons for this are multifactorial; systemic inflammation causes general growth retardation and arrest; local inflammation leads to increased epiphyseal growth and premature closure of growth zones. Negative value also has a negative impact on a large number of joints, reduced motor activity, amyotrophy, chronic intoxication with the subsequent development of dystrophy. However, the most important factor affecting growth seems to be glucocorticoid therapy, its doses and duration of treatment [14,17,30,32,34,39].

Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic inflammatory joint disease of unknown etiology and complex pathogenesis. It is characterized by a steadily progressive course, sometimes involving internal organs, which leads to disability. Among the many extra-articular manifestations of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, one of the leading is growth impairment. In this case, not only the growth process itself suffers, but also forms asymmetry of the child's body. Thus, the body proportions characteristic of early childhood is preserved in children of high school age [6, 29]. B.M. Ansell and E.G.L. Bywaters (1956) showed for the first time on a large statistical material that the growth of children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is affected not only by the disease, but also by corticosteroid therapy aimed at its control [6]. They published their 5-year follow-up of bone growth and development in 119 children under 14 years of age with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis for more than 1 year. According to the studies, active disease delayed overall growth, and corticosteroid treatment exacerbated this delay. Young children treated with glucocorticosteroids in the absence of epiphyseal fusion were shown to have accelerated and catch-up growth during remission. This was not observed in patients with long-term persistent disease activity. In patients who received such therapy for a long time despite control over the activity of the process, there was growth impairment. These studies allowed us to conclude that the severe course of the disease and steroid therapy are factors contributing to growth retardation in juvenile patients. Growth retardation in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, especially in children with severe systemic variants of the disease [33]. Growth retardation is observed not only in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, but also in spondyloarthritis. The results of studies by a number of authors have shown that when juvenile ankylosing spondylitis manifests in adolescence, growth stops despite the increased release of somatotropic hormone during this period [33, 41]. This

indicates that the activity of the disease itself negatively affects the growth process. According to the results of a study by L. Berczi et al. (1986) human growth hormone has a pro-inflammatory and immunostimulatory effect in adjuvant arthritis in rats, which is similar to the manifestations of seronegative spondyloarthritis in humans [33, 47]. Hypothetically, human growth hormone may be one of the triggering factors for the development of juvenile ankylosing spondylitis in a patient with a genetic predisposition [33]. In the study of growth hormone concentration in the serum of patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, contradictory data were obtained. Some studies reported reduced growth hormone levels, while others reported normal levels [13,18,33,47]. R.A. Sturge et al. (1970) first studied juvenile growth and secretion of growth hormone and cortisol in 20 patients with systemic juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

Insulin tolerance tests 10 h after corticosteroid administration were used to assess growth hormone and cortisol secretion. The results of this study revealed a significant suppression of growth hormone secretion in patients receiving daily corticosteroids [43]. More detailed studies were conducted by O. Butenandt et al. (1976), who determined the level of growth hormone secretion also using the insulin tolerance test and proved the fact of impaired secretion of somatotrophic hormone in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis [18]. Later, U.M. Davies et al (1994) studied 24-hour growth hormone profiles in 14 children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. However, no significant differences from similar profiles in healthy children with short stature were found [23]. The study of the peripheral link of the growth regulatory system showed a decrease in the concentration of insulin-like growth factor-1 in patients with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis [11,13,16, 46,]. Disturbances in the circadian rhythm of growth hormone production and loss of physiological nocturnal release were found in patients with high disease activity compared to healthy individuals [11,33,].

Conclusion

Currently, there are few studies investigating growth problems in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. In the available works, a significant growth retardation of these children compared to their healthy peers has been noted. Growth retardation in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis depends on the inflammatory activity of the disease and is particularly pronounced in the systemic variant. However, oral glucocorticosteroids are the main cause of stunting in these children. Stunting is more pronounced when the earlier glucocorticosteroid therapy is started, the longer it has been administered and the higher the dose of prednisolone has been. The debut of the disease at an early age in the type of systemic variants, its continuously recurrent course with high activity lead to growth retardation, which is aggravated by glucocorticosteroid therapy.

Prevention and treatment of growth impairment in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is still one of the unsolved problems.

REFERENCES

1. A.N. Shapovalenko, I.P. Nikishina, A.A. Sharova the problem of growth disturbance in patients with juvenile arthritis Moscow Nauchno-Prakticheskaya Rheumatologiya N 5. 2007 C 74-76.
2. Zvyagintseva S.G., Bolshakova A.M., Dorofeeva T.N. Corticosteroid therapy in children of early age. Proceedings of the Central Institute for Advanced Training of Physicians. 1964; 73: 79-83.

3. I.A. Dauksh. Murathodjaeva A.V., Pirnazarova G.Z., Hakimova U.R. Systemic diseases of connective tissue: juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (features of clinic, diagnosis and modern methods of treatment) / - Tashkent 2018. P-5 UDC: 616-053.2:616.72-002.77 C 40.
4. Ioshpa L.L., Trefilova E.V., Titov G.N. Issues of corticosteroid therapy in pathology of bronchopulmonary system in children. *Paediatrics* 1974; 7(2): 69-73.
5. Kukes V.G. Clinical pharmacology. Moscow: Geotar Medicine, 1999; p. 415.
6. Nasonova V.A., Bunchuk N.V. Rheumatic diseases. Manual on internal diseases. Moscow: Medicine; 1997, 298-299.
7. Nasonova V.A., Bunchuk N.V., Rheumatic diseases. Manual on internal diseases. Moscow: Medicine; 1997, 302.
8. Ryabova T.V., Lyskina G.A., Zhvaniya M.A., Ivanova K.V. Modern methods of treatment of collagen diseases in children. *Paediatrics* 1975; 9. 73-6.
9. T.M. Bzarova, E.I. Alexeeva / *Voprosy sovremennoi paediatrics*, 2003, Vol. 2, No. 3, P 39-42.
10. Kharkevich D.A. Pharmacology. Moscow: Geotar Medicine; 1999, 405.
11. Aitmann T.J., Palmer R.G., Loftus J., et al. Serum IGF-I levels and growth failure in juvenile chronic arthritis. *Clin Exp Rheumatol* 1989; 7: 557-63.
12. Allen D.B. Glucocorticoid-associated growth failure: mechanisms and potential reversal. *Endocrinologist* 1998;8: 21-30.
13. Allen R.C., Jimenez M., Cowell C.T. Insulin-like growth hormone secretion in juvenile chronic arthritis. *Ann Rheumatic Dis* 1991; 5: 602-6.
14. Ansell BM., Ward D.J. Corticosteroid-induced dwarfism in Still's disease treated with human growth hormone. Clinical and metabolic effects including hydroxy- proline excretion in two cases. *And Rheumatic Dis* 1966: 5: 176-27.
15. Avioli L.V. Glucocorticoid effects on statural growth. *Br J Rheumatol* 1993; 32: 27-30.
16. Bennett A.E., Silverman E.C., Miller J.J. III & Hintz R.L. Insulin-like growth factors I and II in children with systemic onset juvenile arthritis. *J Reumatol* 1988; 15: 655-8.
17. Bernstein B.H., Stobie D., Singen B.H., et al Growth retardation in juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheumatism* 1977; 20: 212-6.
18. Butenandt O., Eder R., Clados-Kelch A. Wachstumshormonbestimmungen bei Kindern mit rheumatoider Arthritis und Still-Syndrom. *Verhandlungen Deutschen Gesellschaft Rheumatologie* 1976; 4: 47-53.
19. Cabrielson B.G., Carmignac D.F., Flavel D.M., et al. Steroid regulation of growth hormone (GH) receptor and GH-binding protein messenger ribonucleic acid in the rat. *Endocrinology* 1995; 136: 209-17.
20. Casanueva F.F., Burguera B., Muruais C. et al. Depending on the time of administration, dexamethasone potentiates or blocks growth hormone-releasing hormone-induced growth hormone release in man. *Neuroendocrinology*, 1988, 47, 1, 46-49.
1. 21. Casanueva F.F., Burguera B., Tome M.A., et al. Depending on the time of administration, dexamethasone potentiates or blocks growth hormone-releasing hormone-induced growth hormone release in man. *Neuroendocrinology* 1988; 47: 46-9.
21. Davies U.M. Jones J., Reeve J. et al. Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. Effects of disease activity and recombinant human growth hormone on insulin- like growth factor I insulin-like growth factor binding proteins 1 and 3, and osteocalcin. *Arthritis Rheum.* 1997, 40(2), 332-40.

22. Davies U.M., Rooney M., Preece M.A., et al. Treatment of growth retardation in juvenile chronic arthritis with recombinant human growth hormone. *J. Rheumatol* 1994; 21:153-8.
23. Ekim M., Tumer N. Ocal G., et al. Effect of corticosteroids on growth in children with steroid-sensitive nephrotic syndrome *Child Nephrol Urol* 1992; 12: 10-4.
24. Garcia-Consuegra Molina J., Merino Munoz R., Lama More R. et al. Growth in children with juvenile idiopathic arthritis] [Article in Spanish] *A Peditr. (Barc)*. 2003,58(6),529-537.
25. Gertz B.J., Gardner D.G., Baxter J.D. Glucocorticoid control of rat growth hormone gene expression: effect on cytoplasmic messenger ribonucleic acid production and degradation. *Mol Endocrinol* 1987; 1: 933-41.
26. Growth hormone therapy in the glucocorticosteroid-dependent child: metabolic and linear growth effects. *Horm. Res.* 2001,56, suppl 1,13-18.
27. Guistina A., Bussi A.R., Jacobello C., et al. Effects of recombinant human growth hormone (GH) on bone and intermediary metabolism in patient receiving chronic glucocorticoid treatment with suppressed endogenous GH response to GH-releasing hormone. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1995; 80: 122-9.
28. James T. Cassidy, Ross E. Petty. *Textbook of Pediatric Rheumatology*. 4th ed 2001; 218-321.
29. Laaksonen S.L. A prognostic study of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis: Analysis of 544 cases. *Acta Paediatr Scand* 1966; 149-55.
30. Mehls O., Tonschoff B., Kovacs G., et al. Interaction between glucocorticoids and growth hormone. *Acta Paediatr Scand* 1993; 388: 77-82.
31. Michel's H., Hafner R., Morhart R., et al. Five years follow-up of a prospective cohort of juvenile chronic arthritis with recent onset. *Clin Rheumatol* 1987; 6: 87-92.
32. Neeck G., Federlin K., Graef V., et al, Zirkadiane Variationen der Serumkonzentrationen von Cortisol, Prolactin und Wachstumsormon bei Patienten mit Rheumatoider Arthritis. *Aktuelle Endokrinologie Stoffwechsel* 1988; 9: 57-63.
33. Neeck G., Michels H. Endocrine aspects of paediatric rheumatic diseases. *Bailliere's Clin Rheumatol* 1996; 2: 349-63.
34. Orth Kovacs WAS The adrenal cortex In *Williams Textbook of Endocrinology*. - Wilson JD et al. eds) - 8th edition 1998, 0.517-665.
35. Picco P., Gattorno M., Sormani M.P. et al. Involvement of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in children with oligoarticular-onset idiopathic arthritis. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 2002,966,369-72.
36. Polito C., Strano C.G., Olivieri A.N. et al. Growth retardation in non-steroid treated juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Scand. J. Rheumatol.*, 1997,26(2),99-103.
37. Reeve J., Loftus J., Hesp R. et al. Biochemical prediction of changes in spinal bone mass in juvenile chronic (or rheumatoid) arthritis treated with glucocorticoids. *J. Rheumatol.* 1993,20(7),1189-1195.
38. Sanger L. Klinische Studie über schwere Nachschlumsretardierung bei juveniler rheumatoider Arthritis und Still-Syndrom. *Verhandlungen Deutschen Gesellschaft Rheumatology* 1976; 4: 42-6.
39. Simon D. Touati G., Prieur A.M. et al. Growth hormone treatment of short stature and metabolic dysfunction in juvenile chronic arthritis. *Acta. Paediatr.*, suppl.,88, 100-105.

40. Southwood E Woo P. Juvenile chronic arthritis. In: A.J. Silman, D.P.M. Symmons (eds). *Classification and Assessment of Rheumatic Diseases*. London: Balliere Tindall; 1995; Part I: 331.
41. Strano C.G., Olivieri A.N., Alessio M., Iammarrone C.S., Todisco N., Papale M.R. Growth retardation in non-steroid treated juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Scand. J. Rheumatol.*, 1997, 26, 2, 99-103.
42. Sturge R.A., Bearwell C., Hartog M. Cortisol and growth hormone secretion in relation to linear growth: patients with Still's disease on different therapeutic regimens. *Br Med J* 1970, 547-51.
43. Svantesson H. Treatment of growth failure with human growth hormone in patients with juvenile chronic arthritis. A pilot study. *Clin. Exp. Rheumatol.* 1991, 9, suppl. 6, 47-50.
44. Swolin D., Brantsing C., Matejka G., et al. Cortisol decreases IGF-1 mRNA level in human osteoblasts-like cells. *J Endocrinol* 1996; 149: 397-403.
45. Takami M., Taguchi T., Nagashima K. Endocrinological studies on growth retardation in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Ryumacchi* 1982; 22: 19.
46. Wilder R. Animal models of reactive arthritis. In: L. Espinoza, D. Goldenberg, F. Arnet, et al (eds). *Infections in the Rheumatic Diseases*. Philadelphia, PA: Grune - Stratton: 1988; 45-51.
47. Woo P.M, Growth retardation and osteoporosis in juvenile chronic arthritis. *Clin. Exp. Rheumatol.*, 1994, 12, suppl 10, 87-90.
48. Zak M Muller J, Karup Pedersen F, Final height, armspan, subischial leg length and body proportions in juvenile chronic arthritis. A long-term follow-up studies. *Horm. Res.*, 1999, 52, 2, 80-85.
49. Zak M., Pedersen F.K. Juvenile chronic arthritis into adulthood: a long-term follow-up study *Rheumatology (Oxford)*, 2000, 39, 2, 198-204.
50. Zulian F., Schumacher H.R., Calore A. et al. Juvenile arthritis in Turner's syndrome: a multicenter study. *Clin. Exp. Rheumatol.*, 1998, 16(4), 489-494.